

ANALYSIS OF ANTI-MONOPOLY STRATEGY AND ONGOING
WORK IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the development of the market economy in Uzbekistan today, the importance of competition, anti-monopoly strategy and ongoing work. In order to ensure the balance of the business sectors of the economy, scientifically based conclusions have been developed on the implementation of the state monetary policy and the theoretical aspects of increasing its effectiveness, as well as on further increasing the importance of the policy of providing state support to the business sectors of the economy in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords. *Economy, market economy, competition, anti-monopoly, strategy, business, monetary policy, business management, enterprise.*

For the development of the modern market economy in the country, it is important to preserve the enterprises in the fields where competition should be formed, and to produce a business management mechanism that allows enterprises to adapt to the market conditions. This mechanism assumes that state enterprises will be economically free, and their activities will be commercialized.

Since the main method of competition during the transition to the market economy is the price, the free release of prices is the main requirement for creating a competitive environment. It is important to ensure the development of economic

sectors in the conditions of market relations and to know its prospects in advance on a scientific basis.

As a result of the economic reforms carried out in our country, the real sector of the economy is developing rapidly. The composition of the economy of entrepreneurial activity is a set of various industries and sectors that provide goods and services in the national economy, and they are in economic activity in interaction and dependence. In order to ensure the balance of the business sectors of the economy, scientifically based conclusions have been developed on the implementation of the state monetary policy and the theoretical aspects of increasing its effectiveness, as well as on further increasing the importance of the policy of providing state support to the business sectors of the economy in Uzbekistan.

V.R. was given by many foreign scientists related to issues and problems of the economy of our country and international financial institutions. Bank, O.I. Volkov, Ye.I. Shokhina and others. Uzbek scientists have also developed their own scientific recommendations while analyzing the economic situation related to anti-monopoly management, competitiveness formation and the activity of IMI. Therefore, the main feature of the formation of a monopoly (monopoly) is the acquisition of a monopoly position. The latter is characterized as a dominant position of an entrepreneur, which alone or together with other entrepreneurs gives the opportunity to limit competition in the market for a certain product. A monopoly position is acceptable for every entrepreneur or enterprise, because it allows you to avoid a number of problems and risks related to competition: to gain a privileged position by accumulating a certain economic power in the market; influencing other market participants, imposing their conditions on them.

Monopolists can be considered to impose their personal interests on their counterparties, and sometimes on society. When analyzing monopoly, it is important to consider the ambiguity of the term "monopoly". First of all, the

essence of this phenomenon cannot be deduced from the etymology of the word "mono" - one, "poliomyelitis" - I sell. In fact, it is almost impossible to find a situation in the market where a single firm - the producer of a non-substitute product - operates.

Consequently, there is always a certain amount of convention in the use of the term monopoly, and even more so "pure" monopoly. The formation and growth of monopolies is historically inextricably linked with the transformation of free competition capital into monopoly capitalism. The capitalist growth of monopolies in the field of economic relations led to the strengthening of their dictatorship and rule. Perfect competition and "pure" absolute monopoly are theoretical abstractions representing bipolar market conditions, two logical limits.

Monopolies create opportunities for accelerating technological progress due to the high concentration of economic resources. However, these opportunities are realized in cases where such acceleration is favorable for higher returns. Some economists favor large firms with significant power in the economy because they accelerate technological change because firms with monopoly power can spend their monopoly profits on research to protect or strengthen their monopoly power.

By conducting research, they benefit themselves and society as a whole. But there is no convincing evidence that monopolies play a particularly important role in accelerating technological progress, because monopolies can delay the development of technological progress if their profits are threatened. The objective basis of a monopoly is a dominant position of an economic entity in the market, which allows it to exert a decisive influence on competition, exceeding the volume of production compared to the theoretically possible level, and reduces and prevents market entry for other businesses. subjects.

Ultimately, this allows the monopolist to redistribute effective demand in his favor, making the monopoly more profitable. Competitive markets usually work well, which is not the case in markets where both buyers and sellers can

control prices. In a market where one seller controls supply, output is low and prices are high.

The state can use the following tools to fulfill its tasks. State property, redistribution of national income by the state through the budget, state participation in the credit sector and its control, administrative measures of state economic control. A market economy means equal opportunity, but the use of this opportunity is not the same among people, everyone receives income according to what he earns. Income stratification creates a desire to get rich and encourages people to be economically active.

Although monetary relations prevail in the market economy, human relations that are not related to money: kindness and benevolence also develop. In countries with a developed market economy, large philanthropic funds serve to help the needy and do not aim to extract money from the money. The market economy is constantly developing, its new forms and models appear. Historically, there were 2 types of market economy: wild market economy, civilized market economy. The first market economy appeared as a stable economy during the period of capital accumulation with the development of commodity-money relations, it was characterized by the accumulation of private property in the hands of a few, the dominance of lawlessness and disorder in the economy, the lawless competition, the withdrawal of the state from the economy, the frequent occurrence of deep economic tensions, the lack of social protection of the population, the separation of people into extremely rich and extremely poor classes, and social conflict.

Antichrist economy will grow into enlightened economy through development. Such a change began in the 30s of the 20th century and continued until the 80s in developed market economy countries. The current market economy is a civilized economy, characterized by the following characteristics: ownership diversity, orderly economy, state intervention in the economy, cultural and

competitive competition, strong cooperative relations, short-term and light relief of economic tensions, mass prosperity, lack of deep social stratification, self-sufficiency and the growth of the position of the prosperous middle class, the preservation of social balance and the absence of civil conflicts, etc. These signs characterize the current market economy, but its development is not limited to this.

Anti-monopoly policy - state anti-monopoly policy. According to the world experience, anti-monopoly legislation was mainly formed along the following lines. First, laws governing production (industry). According to these laws, no single enterprise (corporation) is usually allowed to control more than half of the production of any type of product. Second, it stipulates that participants in all large corporations cannot own more than a certain limited amount of stock in other corporations. Thirdly, anti-cartel laws will be introduced, prohibiting prices from being higher or lower than the level determined by market equilibrium, and prohibiting price collusion.

The anti-monopoly policy of the state is aimed at improving the competitive environment in countries whose national economy is formed by competition, and at forming this environment in countries transitioning to a market economy. In 1890, the first law against trusts, which prohibits attempts to establish a monopoly in the market and the abuse of a monopoly position, was adopted in the USA - the Sherman Act.

Anti-monopoly legislation. and the measures necessary for its implementation apply in the forms required by the circumstances of each country. In order to protect the environment of healthy competition in all developed countries, state regulation of various forms of monopolistic activities is carried out. For example, in the United States, state anti-monopoly policy is carried out by the Federal Trade Commission and the Antitrust Department of the Department of Justice, in Russia by the Ministry of Antimonopoly Policy and Business Support,

in Japan and South Korea by the Fair Competition Commission, and in the European Union by the Competition Commission.

Privatization and creation of other forms of ownership at the expense of state property occupy a key place in the policy of Uzbekistan aimed at creating a competitive environment. As a result of privatization, firstly, the property is transferred to the hands of its owners, and secondly, a multi-level economy and a competitive environment are created. In the formation of competition, for enterprises in the sectors of the economy where state-owned enterprises should be preserved, the production of an economic management mechanism that allows them to adapt to the market conditions takes an important place. This mechanism assumes that state enterprises will be economically free, and their activities will be commercialized.

Since the main method of competition in the period of transition to a market economy is price, the free release of prices is the main requirement for creating a competitive environment. For this purpose, the Law "On Restriction of Monopolistic Activities" was adopted in Uzbekistan, and a series of regulatory documents aimed at the development of competition were developed based on it. According to this law, it is forbidden to deliberately create shortages in the market, monopolize prices, prevent competitors from entering the market, and use unfair methods of competition.

Currently, in Uzbekistan, if certain products produced by an enterprise account for more than 35% of such products on the goods market, this enterprise is entered into the State Register as a monopolistic enterprise (for the group of food products, such a criterion level is set at 20%). An enterprise (network) entered into the list of monopolies in the republic from a number of methods in regulating the market position of:

- a) setting the highest price level or profit margin for monopolistic products;

b) methods are used to destroy or crush monopolistic associations that have abused their monopoly position.

On the basis of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Consumers' Rights, special attention is paid to the creation of a mechanism that prevents unfair competition, including the entry of goods that do not meet the specified requirements into the markets.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Limitation of Monopolistic Activities and Competition in Commodity Markets" aims to prevent abuse of the dominant position by monopolists and eliminate monopolies and create a healthy competitive environment. It is not economically feasible to create a competitive environment in some sectors of the economy. Enterprises in this industry are usually called "natural monopolies". The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Natural Monopolies" defines the legal basis of the state policy regarding natural monopolies in the republic.

Anti-monopoly and natural monopolies legislation is being improved based on the essence of economic reforms in Uzbekistan, ensuring their compliance with the European Union and other developed legal standards.

In life, it is impossible to deny secret agreements and secret cartels between sellers against the interests of consumers. It is worth noting that in densely populated big cities with monopolistic land rents, the monopoly profits of their owners from tenants remain the basis.

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